

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

Interim Products Establishment for Cross-Task Collaboration

Milestone Number	4
Milestone Title	Interim Products Establishment for Cross-Task Collaboration
Version n°	1.0
Status	Final
Type	R- Document, report
Dissemination Level	Public
Work Package	WP1
Lead Beneficiary	TUWIEN
Delivery Date	31/07/2024
Author(s)	Tomasz Miksa, Marek Suchánek, Lukas Arnhold, Tassos Stavropoulos, Paolo Manghi
Editor(s)	Tomasz Miksa (TUWIEN)
Reviewers	Jakub Jirka (CODE), Mathieu Servillat (OBSParis)
Approved by	Natalia Manola (OpenAIRE)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe framework programme under grant agreement No. 101130187. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

Revision History

VERSION	STATUS	DATE	DESCRIPTION	AUTHOR(S)
0.1	Draft	05.05.2024	Outline of the document created	Tomasz Miksa
0.9	Ready for internal review	12.07.2024	Contents ready for the internal review	Tomasz Miksa
1.0	Ready for submission	29.07.2024	Milestone document ready for submission	Tomasz Miksa

Authors List

ORGANISATION	NAME	CONTACT INFORMATION
CTU	Marek Suchánek	marek.suchanek@cvut.cz
OpenAIRE	Paolo Manghi	paolo.manghi@openaire.eu
	Tassos Stavropoulos	tassos.stavropoulos@openaire.eu
TUW	Tomasz Miksa	tomasz.miksa@tuwien.ac.at
	Lukas Arnhold	lukas.arnhold@tuwien.ac.at
UPM	Mark Wilkinson;	mark.wilkinson@upm.es
	Daniel Garijo	daniel.garijo@upm.es

Contribution List

ORGANISATION	NAME	CONTACT INFORMATION
ObsParis	Baptiste Cecconi	baptiste.cecconi@obspm.fr
CTU	Jana Martínková	jana.martinkova@cvut.cz
Codevence	Jakub Jirka	jakub.jirka@codevence.com
University of Oxford (UOXF)	Susanna-Assunta Sansone; Allyson Lister; Milo Thurston	susanna-assunta.sansone@oerc.ox.ac.uk allyson.lister@oerc.ox.ac.uk milo.thurston@oerc.ox.ac.uk
KNAW-DANS	Wilko Steinhoff	wilko.steinhoff@dans.knaw.nl
	Wim Hugo	wim.hugo@dans.knaw.nl
OpenAIRE	Leonidas Pispiringas	leonidas.pispiringas@openaire.eu
European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF)	Renaud Duyme	renaud.duyme@esrf.fr
CITE	Georgios Kakalettris	gkakas@cite.gr
LifeWatch ERIC	Joaquín López Lérída	joaquin.lopez@lifewatch.eu
University of Vienna	Daniel Spichtinger	daniel.spichtinger@univie.ac.at
ARC	Elli Papadopoulou	elli.p@athenarc.gr

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The publication herein was produced in the framework of the EU-funded OSTrails project (Grant Agreement No 101130187). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the OSTrails consortium and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Abbreviations list

AAI Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure

API Application Programming Interface

CRIS Current Research Information System

DMP Data Management Plan

DSW Data Stewardship Wizard

maDMP Machine-Actionable DMPs

RDA Research Data Alliance

SKG Scientific Knowledge Graph

Executive Summary

This milestone report (M4) for the EU-funded OSTrails project presents key developments and progress up to month 6. It consists of four main sections: architecture and Interoperability Frameworks' definition, FAIRness model baseline, pilots, and the dissemination and engagement roadmap. This document provides a snapshot of the current developments and the results presented here should not be considered final.

Architecture and Interoperability Frameworks: Based on the deliverable D1.1 Plan-Track-Assess Pathways, we developed an initial draft of the OSTrails architecture and identified key requirements for Interoperability Frameworks. Specifically, the project will develop three APIs for accessing machine-actionable Data Management Plans (DMPs), Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), and FAIR assessment tools. The specific pilot requirements and data model investigations drive developments of these APIs. The first stable draft of the architecture and interoperability frameworks is set for month 12 of the project.

FAIRness Testing and Baseline Definition: We created and distributed a "Digital Object Survey" to all thematic pilots to gain a comprehensive understanding of the various digital object types used within the OSTrails thematic pilots. At the time of writing, the survey is still ongoing. The results of the survey will help us in defining assessments that are contextually sensitive. This means that while some FAIR tests are considered "core" and applicable to all digital objects in any context (such as the requirement for a Globally Unique Identifier), OSTrails will also define and deploy tests specific to certain types of digital objects. Furthermore, we will include actionable guidance in the FAIR model baseline, shifting from merely assessing compliance to assisting in achieving it.

Pilots: We organized separate meetings for national and thematic pilots to align objectives and gather insights. Two surveys identified the pilots' use cases and integration plans, showing varied participation and strong engagement in developing machine-actionable DMPs tailored to national requirements.

Dissemination and Engagement: We established a comprehensive roadmap for dissemination and engagement, including communication strategies and key performance indicators (KPIs). This roadmap outlines plans for community engagement and exploitation to ensure wide adoption and utilization of the project's outcomes.

1. Draft Architecture and Interoperability Frameworks

In this section, we present the results of ongoing work to define the OSTrails architecture and respective Interoperability Frameworks (IFs).

We discuss how the three key components: DMP Platforms, SKGs, and FAIR assessment tools, can interact to support existing and novel use cases that bring value to different stakeholders active in the management of digital objects.

We base our discussion on the analysis of existing tools and services that the members of the consortium develop and operate. For each of them, we collected use case diagrams depicting their main interactions, interfaces, and data models used. We grouped them and generalized them to get a tool-independent view of the expected connections and integrations needed. In this document, we report the aggregated results of the analysis.

1.1. Methodology

We performed a multi-step consultation within the consortium to identify existing and expected interactions between tools and services. The consultation helped us identify pathways (D1.1), key architecture components (section 3.2), and requirements for the interoperability frameworks (section 3.3). In the remainder of this section, we present the key steps in the consultation process.

1. Conceptual components – the goal was to get a better picture of how tools and services interact with each other, e.g. what information they consume and what information they provide. To do so, each tool/service owner provided an informal sketch of his or her service focusing on the communication to the outside. The conceptual components of their services depicted existing and expected integrations. We deliberately did not follow any formal representation language to make sure that participants were not limited by its expressivity. A list of conceptual components can be found in **Table 1**.
2. Generic conceptual elements – we analysed the components and grouped them into classes of tools and services based on similarities among them (see **Figure 1**). In this step, we wanted to abstract the representation of the components to come up with a generic/universal component that is not specific to a particular tool or service. For example, most DMP tools connect to project/grant registries to get information on projects – hence the conceptual component includes such an interface. The generic conceptual components became a basis for a more structured discussion on the interactions between components and influenced the pathways, architecture, and interoperability frameworks.

Figure 1: Consolidation of conceptual components into generic conceptual components.

3. Pathways – the discussion on the conceptual elements provides the logical view of the OSTrails architecture, and the pathways provide the process view, i.e. they tell how these components are used together to deliver value to the stakeholders. In other words, pathways allow us to identify which component integrations are more common or have higher priority. For example, the pathways tell us how DMP tools are used with other components during research to get automated feedback on FAIRness and DMP quality. A dedicated deliverable D1.1 describes pathways in detail.
4. Architecture – a result of putting two layers onto each other: pathways and underlying generic conceptual elements connected with each other that are necessary to realize the pathway – see **Figure 2**. The architecture does not include any specific tools or services. The architecture can later be instantiated in selected pilots/use cases using specific tools/services. **Figure 2** shows that specific components can have many interactions – also with components that are not part of the pathways – not in the core focus of OSTrails.
5. Interoperability Frameworks – we identified existing standards and are discussing necessary improvements within the project. We also reached out to other EOSC projects and communities like RDA to identify what is currently being developed outside of the project that we may rely on. The blue boxes in **Figure 2** depict the interoperability frameworks relevant for both the pathways and the architecture. It may happen that the IFs will be used by other components that are out of scope of this project (in **Figure 2** these are depicted as boxes that are not within any of the Pathways but have arrows pointing to/from the component that is within the pathway).

Figure 2: Generic conceptual components connected, and pathways projected onto them to form the conceptual architecture – a methodology for deriving the architecture.

1.2. Architecture

This section presents ongoing work to define the OSTrails architecture. It is based on the needs identified in the pathways and aims at bringing clarity on how specific developments addressed by respective tasks of the project fit together. The first draft of the architecture is expected in M12 in D1.3.

Figure 3 depicts the high-level view of the OSTrails architecture. There are four conceptual components:

- DMP Platform - Platform, tool, or service (software system) for data management planning, producing data management plans (DMPs) and potentially machine-actionable data management plans (maDMPs).
- SKG - any database/repository with information pertaining to research products, process and actors & agents which can present a graph-type view on this information via a suitable API.
- FAIR assessment tool - application of a set of one or more FAIR Tests against a digital resource.
- Other – to represent any other tool or service that wants to interact with any of the other three components.

DMP Platform, SKG, and FAIR assessment Tool component provide their own APIs to which other components can connect. These APIs are based on the respective Interoperability Frameworks.

DMP Platform, SKG, and FAIR assessment Tool can also connect to other components using the APIs exposed by them. This is indicated using the unlabelled lollipop symbols. For example, DMP Platform can connect to SKG using the SKG API exposed by the SKG component.

Given that this architecture can be instantiated in many different ways, i.e. there are many possibilities for integration between components, we have used the cloud symbol in the middle of **Figure 3** to avoid connecting all the components with all the interfaces.

In future iterations of the architecture, we will provide more architectural views and include other components that contextualise our project. For example, authentication and authorisation interfaces, repositories, registries, or other services developed by OSTrails, such as the DMP Evaluation Service.

Figure 3. Current draft of the OSTrails architecture depicting three main components and showing the role of Interoperability Frameworks.

1.3. Interoperability Frameworks

According to the proposed methodology, we conducted a survey with the consortium to identify existing and expected interactions between tools and services, with a focus on interactions with the component outlined in the draft of the OSTrails Architecture, being DMP Platform, SKG and FAIR Assessment Tool. Based on the results of the survey, we propose interoperability frameworks for DMP Platforms, SKGs and FAIR Assessment Tools.

For each of these interoperability frameworks we provide following details:

- **Conceptual component** of a service with the required and provided OSTrails interfaces.
- Expected classes of **users** that need to be considered.
- **Functions** that need to be provided by platforms to support pathways.
- **Models** that are relevant for the standardisation and alignment of platforms.

Table 1 Summary of a Survey for integration of Tools and Services through Interoperability Frameworks.

MENTIONED CONCEPTUAL COMPONENTS				
SURVEY ITEM	FOCUS	DMP PLATFORM	SKG	FAIR ASSESSMENT
Argos	Depicts Argos DMP Platform and interactions with other Systems such as Registries, SKGs and FAIR Assessment Tools through proposed OSTrails APIs.	x	x	x
Astronomy Feedback	Community Implementation shows the interactions of a DMP Platform with a variety of Sources and an implementation of a FAIR assessment solution.	x	x	x
DAMAP	Shows the APIs of the DAMAP DMP Platform and includes a proposal of interactions with an OSTrails API to expose DMP information.	x		
DSW	Conceptual view of the Data Stewardship Wizard DMP Platform.	x		
FAIR Validator	Depicts the interactions of a FAIR Assessment Service with other services and highlights parts of the data exposed by such a service.	x	x	x
FAIRsharing	Highlights how different tools and services can benefit from the information on standards, repositories and policies in FAIRsharing, and gives an overview of its APIs	x	x	x
OpenOrgs	Presents a tool for the disambiguation of organizations which provides enriched and deduplicated metadata for various other services. A OSTrails API is proposed to exchange metadata with SKGs.	x	x	x

Lenticular Lens	Depicts a service which accesses SKGs through a proposed OSTrails API.		x	
SSHOC Clarin	Depicts a service which accesses SKGs through a proposed OSTrails API.		x	
PaNOSC Architecture Feedback	Gives an overview of a community implementation which integrates a DMP Platform with Repositories / SKGs and FAIR Tools. It highlights how PaNOSC used these services to satisfy their use cases.	x	x	x
RO-Crate-ROHub	Highlights how the RO-Crate platform (ROHub) can be integrated into the OSTrails landscape through a proposed OSTrails API which exposes SKGs, DMP Platforms and FAIR Assessment Tools.	x	x	x
SKG_generic	Depicts the interactions of a generic SKG with other resources and services and proposes a OSTrails API for the interactions of DMP Tools, DMP Validation Tools and FAIR Tools with OSTrails compliant SKGs.	x	x	x
SSH Data Citation Service	Presents a service which interacts with SKGs and proposed an OSTrails API for the interactions with SKGs.		x	
CESSDA	CESSDA offers data services to the social sciences. The given survey item gives an overview how their services could be integrated with DMP Platforms, SKGs and FAIR Assessment Tools through an OSTrails API.	X	X	x
DMP Evaluator Service	This item depicts a proposal of a DMP Evaluation Service and highlights the associated interfaces. It furthermore shows the connection with DMP Tools, SKGs and FAIR Assessment Services through an OSTrails API.	x	x	x

1.3.1. DMP IF

One of the main goals of the DMP IF is “the standardisation on how DMP platforms model and exchange maDMPs” and specifically the creation of “maDMP application profile and guidelines for anyone willing to exchange maDMPs within EOSC” – as stated in the project proposal.

DMP Platforms (**Figure 4**) encapsulate processes involved in managing DMPs. They provide endpoints to create, edit and export DMPs. In addition to information about the DMP itself, DMP platforms also abstract the results from DMP and FAIR evaluation services and make them accessible.

Figure 4. Generic Conceptual Component of a DMP Platform.

Based on the consultations we performed and on the identified pathways, we consider the following stakeholders when designing the DMP IF:

- **DMP contributors:** Principal Investigators (PIs) and other research project contributors that work with a specific DMP
- **DMP reviewers/support:** data stewards / institutional staff that may contribute (not necessarily directly) to various DMPs
- **DMP Platform administrators/operators:** institutional staff operating the DMP platform (and possibly other RDM services)
- **DMP Platform integrators/consumers (API users):** use information from maDMPs in other services or to produce different resources; or pulls information for the DMP(s) from other resources (write into maDMP)
- **DMP Platform developers:** develop new features, fix and improve the bugs, or otherwise maintain the codebase of the platform or its parts (e.g. plugins)

To support the identified pathways, the DMP platforms should support following functions:

- **Exposing DMPs to (any) other services**
 - Access single DMP
 - Access/filter/query parts of a single DMP
 - Query/search/filter collection of DMPs
 - Methods: (1) List method acts as a registry of DMPs that can be filtered based on important LOD facets (ORCID, RoR, ...) - for implementation of

DMP harvesting, type-ahead lookups, and similar functionalities, and (2) obtaining a detailed maDMP document based on an identifier.

To design: DMP API (read)

- **Notifying other services about “interesting changes” in DMPs**
 - Notify subscribed services about specific events related to the/a DMP (e.g. creation of a new DMP, change of a DMP – informing other services about planned actions, publishing a DMP, etc.)

To design: API for receiving notifications, API for subscriptions, taxonomy of “interesting events”

- **Consuming notifications about “DMP-related interesting changes” from other services**
 - Receive and process subscribed notifications from other services related to DMPs (e.g. dataset published in repository, related resource evaluated, change in dataset metadata, change in related records such as databases, standard, or policies, result of FAIR/DMP evaluation, etc.)

To design: mechanism for receiving notifications and managing the related subscriptions, taxonomy of “interesting events”

- **Pushing DMPs to other services**
 - Send DMP (possibly with additional resources) to an external service (such as repository, DMP registry, or DMP/FAIR evaluation service)
 - For DMP/FAIR evaluation, we expect the mechanism specification to be covered as part of **FAIR-IF**.

To design: versatile/common mechanism how other services accept DMPs (e.g. rely on maDMPs as payloads)

- **Allowing other services to contribute to DMPs (modify/create/populate)**
 - Contributing to a DMP as a whole (e.g. evaluation or review)
 - Affecting parts/entities of a DMP (e.g. add/change/remove dataset, policy, contributors, etc.)
 - Additionally, there are other aspects of DMPs in platforms that might allow contributions from other systems:
 - Creating a new DMP from other service (e.g. CRIS)
 - Change of status/settings (e.g. change of phase, change permissions, archiving, creation of a new version/revision, etc.)

To design: mechanism for handling changes; possibly using / resulting to DMP API (create, update, delete), permission model (AAI), maDMP extension to pull information from other services/resources to populate parts of the DMP

- **Listing/searching records from other tools**

- Search and retrieve a list of DMP-relevant records (policies, standards, databases, projects, contributors, licenses, tools, funders, etc.) from external services (registries, databases, CRIS etc.)
- For SKGs, this will be ensured by **SKG-IF**; however, all other services holding records relevant to DMPs should be also aligned for interoperability with DMP platforms (and possibly other tools)

To design: endpoint for other tools/services and the machine-actionability within the IF (e.g. their API and data schemata) for listing records from various external services, on boarding guidelines for services so they can be linked with DMP IF

The RDA Common Standard for machine-actionable DMPs¹ is the common way of providing information on maDMPs and we will build on top of it. Yet, we identified a set of improvements that further empower interoperability:

- **Data model** and exchange formats for the APIs (not to become available in the first iteration)
 - OSTrails extension of the RDA DMP Common Standard for maDMPs
 - Include other research outputs incl. software (as stated in the proposal)
 - Allow further extensions (by infrastructures, domain-specific communities, tools, institutions, and others)
 - Aligned with existing widely used ontologies and vocabularies (schema.org, DataCite, Dublin Core, SKOS, Codemeta, etc.)
- **Schema for notifications** (potentially reusing existing one based on W3C Web Notifications)
- **Uniform schema(s) for records** from other services
- **Schema for results and metadata of DMP evaluation** (aligned with FAIR tests and DMP Common Standard / its extension)

1.3.2. SKGs IF

Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) provide access to scholarly linked data in a uniform format through different types of endpoints. They also provide endpoints for editing and curating the contained data and data model represents scholarly data which is interlinked. Besides being a central access point to this information, SKGs act as a semantic normalization layer supporting information exchange between the different SKGs.

As specified in the DoA, OSTrails will build on and contribute to the results of the Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF) Working Group in RDA.² The main

¹<https://archive.rd-alliance.org/group/dmp-common-standards-wg/outcomes/rda-dmp-common-standard-machine-actionable-data-management>

²<https://www.rd-alliance.org/rationale/scientific-knowledge-graphs-interoperability-framework-skg-if-wg/>

goal of the WG is the standardization of how SKGs model and exchange structured scholarly data, and specifically aim to create an “SKG-IF application profile and APIs guidelines for anyone willing to exchange SKG data within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)”.

The SKG-IF data model is available at <https://skg-if.readthedocs.io> and is illustrated in **Figure 6**. The current model includes the following core entities, common to known Scientific Knowledge Graphs, otherwise known as Scholarly Knowledge Graphs, such as DataCite, Crossref, OpenAIRE Graph, OpenAlex, OKRG, and OpenCitations: Research Products, Persons, Organisations, Venues, Data sources, Grants, and Topics.

In order to support the needs and perspectives of the research communities, OSTrails will suggest some initial changes and additions to the existing SKG-IF and discuss these in the RDA SKG-IF WG. Inspired by the information available from the research community's rich metadata records these changes and additions concern aspects of terminology and research data creation and analysis e.g. instrument and facility usage, long-term research activities modelled in a single Project need changes to existing entities and new entities. Additionally, a suitable extension mechanism will be part of the new SKG-IF to support future changes in a flexible way. Since there is still ongoing work evident from the SKG-IF WG, alignment and further collaboration between OSTrails stakeholders and the SKG-IF WG is in place.

Figure 5 shows that SKGs are services that encapsulate processes involved in managing and interconnecting scholarly metadata collected from a set of scholarly data sources, such as repositories, archives, databases, etc. SKGs provide endpoints through which searching, retrieving, and accessing metadata records and links collected from different sources can be de-duplicated and enriched.

Figure 5 Generic Conceptual Component of a SKG Platform

Based on the consultations and on the identified pathways, we consider the following stakeholders when designing the SKG-IF:

- **SKG Users:** Researchers and other contributors that work with specific SKG entries.
- **SKG Platform Providers/Operators:** staff operating the SKG platform
- **SKG Platform consumers (API users):** users or services utilizing content from SKGs in other services or to produce different resources
- **SKG Platform Developers:** developing and maintaining the software and infrastructure of the SKG platforms

To support the identified pathways, SKG platforms should support the following functions:

- **Support access to metadata and links in SKGs from other services:**
 - **Random access to single SKG record:** allows the retrieval of a single record in the SKG by ID (local or PIDs).
 - **Query SKG to get a collection of records:** support search and retrieval of records in SKG based on criteria.
 - **Resolve ID by relationship type to get related records:** support retrieval of records that are linked to a given record ID by means of a relationship type (e.g., supplementedBy, cited, relatedTo, partOf); e.g. all datasets (records) “cited by” a given publication (record).

To Design: SKG APIs

- **Notifying other services about “interesting events” regarding records in SKGs:**
 - Notify subscribed data source services about specific events related to SKGs: For example, enrichment of a record with properties or links that are not available at the data source site.

To Design: API for retrieving notifications, API for sending subscriptions, taxonomy of “Interesting Events”

- **Allowing other services to contribute to SKGs (modify/create):**
 - Other services with relevant information can provide additional information to one or more SKGs. To avoid security/integrity issues if done automatically this should be by a “pull” rather than push process.
 - Creating a new SKG record or link: for example, dedicated UIs that enable users to apply changes to the SKG or third-party service pushing records within the SKG.

To Design: SKG API (Create, Update, Delete), Permission Model (AAI)

The RDA Interoperability Framework for SKGs defines a common way of exchanging information from/to/between SKGs. With the contribution of OSTrails, the SKG-IF model has been extended with the notion of *extensions*, in order to upgrade the framework with the ability to integrate its scholarly-oriented data model with scientific declinations. This approach ensures that the SKGs are technically interoperable and usable across a wide range of research disciplines and infrastructures, facilitating more effective and efficient scholarly communication and data integration.

Figure 6 SKG-IF Data Model

1.3.3. FAIR IF

FAIR Assessment Tools provide access to their implementation of FAIR Tests (high granularity) or FAIR Benchmarks (low granularity; composites of FAIR Tests) – see **Figure 7**. The exposed interfaces provide the possibility to:

- Discover appropriate Tests or Benchmarks via query of their metadata
- Execute an assessment of a digital object either by:
 - Executing a single test (high granularity), or
 - Executing a suite of tests that represent an objective or benchmark for a specific community

Figure 7 Generic Conceptual Component of FAIR Tool Component

Based on the consultations and on the identified pathways, we consider the following stakeholders when designing the FAIR-IF:

Classes of users

- **FAIR tool developer:** developer of a FAIR tool that aims to interoperate with the OSTRails framework
- **Validation tools:** Software that needs to engage with FAIR assessment software to complete their tasks, i.e., DMP validation software
- **FAIR tool user:** researcher with a digital object that may be subject to FAIR assessment
- **SKG developer:** developer of a SKG platform who wishes to assign FAIR assessment scores to their digital objects
- **SKG hosts:** The outcomes of FAIR assessments for any kind of Digital Object should be stored for rapid lookup - these will become part of an SKG and will thereby be connected to the digital objects they reference

Expected functions and list of eligible corresponding APIs (may not all be available in first iteration)

- Exposing Test Implementation metadata
- Exposing FAIR Metric metadata
- Exposing FAIR Benchmark metadata
- Initiate Test execution and retrieval of results
- Initiate Algorithm execution and retrieval of results

Data model and exchange formats for the APIs (may not all be available in first iteration)

- Data model for exchanging Test results
- Data model for exchanging Test Set results (i.e., the tests associated with an execution of a Benchmark Algorithm)
- Data model for exchanging Test, Metric, and Benchmark metadata
 - These will be registered in the OSTRails Commons (WP2)

Governance (API to be determined)

FAIR Tests are created by a wide range of stakeholders, most of whom are not in the OSTRails project. To ensure consistency and quality control, all Tests, Test Implementations, and Metrics will be subject to a peer-review prior to being registered in the OSTRails Commons. The degree to which submission of a Test or Metric to the nascent Governance process taking place will become increasingly automated as the project matures. This will be done in collaboration with the EOSC-A Task Force on FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects.

2. FAIRness model baseline

Context: FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) refers to a set of guidelines for contemporary digital object publications. FAIR emphasizes features of the publication metadata and data that should be present to enable an automated agent to discover and appropriately reuse the data. In this context, “appropriately” means selecting the right data, for the right task, for the right expert community, under the correct access and usage conditions, and with proper citation. Because FAIR refers to features that should be utilized by computational agents, agents can be designed that specifically look for these features, and report back on their success or failure. In OSTrails, these are called “FAIR Assessment tools”, and there are several tasks related to defining how these tools should behave, their interfaces, harmonization between them, and how to use/interpret their outputs. Given the ability to test for FAIRness, an obvious question becomes: What is an adequate score? Is there a “baseline” for FAIRness that could or should be defined by OSTrails?

OSTrails Objectives: With respect to FAIR Assessment, OSTrails has set itself the task of ensuring that Assessments are contextually-sensitive; that is, while some FAIR tests might be considered “core” (i.e. applicable to all digital objects in all contexts, for example, the requirement for a Globally Unique Identifier), OSTrails will also define, and deploy, tests that are only applicable to certain types of digital objects. To get a realistic insight of all such digital object types used within the OSTrails thematic pilots, a “Digital Object Survey” was created and has been sent to all thematic pilots. At the time of writing, the survey is still ongoing. Even more precisely, OSTrails will provide a “framework” to define community tests on an object-by-object basis. These tests will be demonstrated with WP4 Pilots.

FAIRness Testing in General: Assessments of FAIRness, particularly when applied by third parties, are fraught with controversy. With agencies and journals increasingly making FAIRness a requirement, the “FAIRness score” of digital objects begins to have significance. Moreover, since the publication of a digital object will most frequently utilize a specialist or generalist repository, the content/quality of the metadata is often the responsibility of the host repository, rather than the data creator. Thus, certain FAIRness expectations may be unachievable in some circumstances (e.g. when there is no automatable way to access the metadata provided by the data creator, due to it not being exposed through the repository interface).

Defining a “baseline” for FAIRness: Given the points raised above, it is important to be thoughtful about how we define “baselines for FAIRness” or “minimal levels of FAIRness”. There are two immediately apparent difficulties when considering “baselines”: 1) Have the correct tests been applied, in a fair way, such that the provider could in all circumstances have passed the test? and 2) when considering an overall “score”, are some

tests more important than others, and does that vary between communities, or between different stakeholder groups who observe the assessment output? Both appear to be sufficient barriers that consideration of a “baseline” (or even multiple baselines) will become unmanageable and will almost certainly lead to friction between the assessment teams and the pilots who are being assessed. It is, however, useful to execute assessments, since those will tell an agent (human or automated) what FAIR behaviours a digital object supports, and this can help automated agents in their selection of what digital objects to recommend.

In OSTrails we will therefore define the FAIRness model baseline in terms of transparency - that is, the digital object must make its FAIR assessment output available for scrutiny by an agent. There are two ways that this requirement can be met, which are chosen by the (a) simplicity and/or (b) openness of the data:

1. The digital object must be sufficiently “simple” and “open” that an agent can dynamically apply an Assessment and retrieve a score within a reasonable time.
2. For complex/large digital objects, or for digital objects that cannot be made publicly available, the appropriate FAIR assessment (see below) must be run by the provider, and the results published in the metadata record of that digital object or some other appropriate location, for example, a dedicated SKG for assessment outputs.

In collaboration with the OSTrails thematic and national pilots, we will be creating a matrix of digital object types, and what FAIR assessments should be executed over those, on a community-by-community basis. This will extend knowledge of the same type that has already been collected in the knowledge graph of FAIR Implementation Profiles (Schultes et al., 2020). Thus, OSTrails will be defining what is the appropriate assessment metric that should be applied, and these test outputs should be made available to exploration agents. Data providers may also decide to provide alternative assessment outputs to highlight other FAIR features that they support, but these will be in addition to the metric defined by OSTrails. The schema used to publish these reports is still under development. The work carried out on the requirements and specifications of FAIR assessment reports are described in a GitHub repository.³ Currently, four main concepts are being described (TestResult, TestSpecification, TestResultSet and TestExecutionActivity), including their relations and their serialisations (e.g. interoperability). The inventory of FAIR test metadata has also started. It is an attempt to define all metadata fields that describe a FAIR test which should be used within OSTrails. It will improve the discovery of FAIR tests and may serve to document them. Test metadata should become part of the baseline.

Guidance should be integral to FAIR assessments to ensure transparency and prevent misuse or misinterpretation, and therefore part of the baseline. FAIR Test results should

³ https://github.com/OSTrails/FAIR_assessment_output_specification

be complemented by user guidance, to facilitate their implementation at any stage of the research lifecycle. In OSTrails, we will include guidance in the FAIR model baseline, shifting from merely assessing FAIR compliance to assisting in achieving it by providing actionable guidance rather than judgment in the end. The infrastructure used to gather and provide this guidance is still under development within the project and is dependent on the results of other (sub) tasks.

3. Pilots

WP4 has initiated its activities by organizing separate meetings for national and thematic pilots. The objectives of these meetings were to update the pilots on the project's progress including information about the technical developments from WP1 to WP3, as well as the dissemination efforts from WP5. *Vice versa* the national pilots have provided updates about their status in the initial stage of the project.

For both national and thematic pilots, the aim was to initially identify the pilots' intentions regarding future integrations planned within the project. To achieve this, two surveys were conducted. The first was designed to ascertain which use cases the pilots will be working on to determine the levels of integration each pilot aims to achieve. It should be noted that those use cases will be analysed in the D4.1 Pilots Methodology and Operational Processes that is currently underway. The second and more detailed survey aimed to gather insights into the state of play of the national pilots in their respective ecosystems, including the future development plans of the pilots. It is important to note that all these tasks are focused on defining the methodology, as the specific tasks related to both types of pilots will not commence until month 18 (M18) of the project.

3.1. Survey Conducted for National Pilots

The analysis revealed that there was substantial participation in some use cases, while others had less involvement. Specifically, all national pilots showed strong engagement in use case I, which focuses on developing machine-actionable Data Management Plan (maDMP) templates tailored to address national funders and local infrastructure requirements, including Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) repositories. In contrast, only a few national pilots indicated intentions to work on use case VI, which aims to extend national monitoring systems and funder reporting systems with maDMPs. The detailed results are as follows:

- Use Case I: Full participation from all national pilots
- Use Case II: Mixed involvement with 7-8 pilots fully participating, 1 not participating, and 4-5 uncertain
- Use Case III: A balanced distribution with 4 pilots each showing full, no, and uncertain participation, and 2 offering optional contributions
- Use Case IV: Engagement from 5 pilots, 3 non-participants, 3 uncertain, and 2 offering optional contributions
- Use Case V: Participation from 5-6 pilots, 5 non-participants, 2-3 uncertain, and 1 offering optional contributions
- Use Case VI: Minimal engagement with 2 pilots participating, 9 not participating, 3 uncertain, and 2 offering optional contributions for the uncertain category

Furthermore, national pilots reported the following details about their activities:

- **Croatia:** Croatia's pilot focuses on three main areas (i) Translating funder requirements into machine-actionable DMPs using Argos, (ii) Enhancing the workflow to archive DMPs into the national repository, which is currently possible only for PDFs and (iii) reporting about DMPs in the national Current Research Information System (CRIS).
- **Finland:** Finland's efforts centre on designing a machine-actionable DMP template for national use, aligned with Research Council Finland's requirements and beneficial for around 60 organizations. The initiative involves 32 organizations in a consortium and has conducted a kick-off and three workshops with about 40 members each, conducted in Finish and English. They are also monitoring and comparing technical tools, considering a national license for a chosen tool.
- **Netherlands:** The Netherlands held a workshop titled "Behind the Data Management Plan of the Future" during the SURF Research Day, emphasizing the importance of integrated workflows. This includes combining ethics approval with GDPR compliance into a single document to reduce administrative workload for researchers. They are interested in how other countries approach these integrations.
- **Poland:** Poland's focus is on integrated workflows and the research data lifecycle, specifically using ARGOS. They have translated ARGOS into Polish and work on the integration with the research object hub. Their end goal is to address pain points for researchers by including pre-defined templates with institution-relevant information, including GDPR compliance. There are plans to integrate with national project submission systems and data repositories, with interest from the National Science Center.
- **Czech Republic:** The Czech Technical University (CTU) in Prague is engaging with Czech funders, including the Grant Agency and the Technology Agency. A significant EOSC implementation project has started to build a national infrastructure for data management, creating potential synergies. Developments of the national DMP tool and the Data Stewardship Wizard, continue, with potential integration with scientific knowledge graphs being explored.
- **Sweden:** Sweden joined the project late and is currently identifying partners, involving discussions with universities and the Research Council. A long-standing collaboration exists with one university. Workshops were held in May, with more planned for September/October to inform data management support officers (approximately 150 people).
- **Portugal:** Portugal has initiated regular meetings between the University of Minho and the National funder to coordinate efforts. The exercise of answering a questionnaire has been beneficial for reflecting on decisions and approaches, with more in-depth work expected in the coming months.
- **Greece:** Greece is working with the Hellenic Academic Libraries consortium on integrating Argos with their data repository infrastructure.

The other national pilots are in the process of setting up their activities.

3.2. Survey Conducted for Thematic Pilots

The thematic pilots survey collected data from various of them focussing on enhancing the integration with OSTrails results from WP1-3. Although the survey is ongoing, we obtained the following information.

The SSHOC/CLARIN pilot aims to extend the European CLARIN catalogue into a comprehensive SKG. This initiative is committed to strengthening the FAIR principles by incorporating FAIR assessments for published datasets. The expected outcome is the development of an enriched SKG that interacts with other SKGs, enhancing data sharing and interoperability.

The FAIRsharing for cross Science Clusters pilot focuses on enhancing the FAIRsharing collections across multiple scientific domains and each Cluster. This pilot emphasizes the use of appropriate standards, databases, and policies in enabling the FAIR principles. The collaborative enrichment of FAIRsharing and its integration with a number of tools are the primary goals of the pilot, which also aims at streamlining the creation and population of maDMPs, and guide the FAIR assessments/assistance processes.

The PaNOSC/ESRF-SOLEIL pilot involves the implementation of automated ma-DMPs and improved metadata for better data strategy planning in photon and neutron facilities. This project is particularly focused on enhancing the FAIRness of datasets and metadata, with the expected outcome of improving the quality and visibility of scientific outputs.

The MASER/ObsParis pilot is implementing a DMP tool tailored to low-frequency radio astronomy. This pilot aims to enhance the FAIRness of datasets and services by utilizing community-tailored assessment tools. The project's goals include better data management practices and improved monitoring of the data lifecycle.

The ESCAPE/CTAO/ObsParis pilot is focused on managing data for the Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory (CTAO). This pilot emphasizes the need for detailed data provenance and FAIR assessment, aiming to develop interfaces compatible with SKGs and propose FAIR assessment criteria for astronomy data.

The JERICO-RI pilot focuses on creating an e-infrastructure for coastal resources, emphasizing the data lifecycle of Glider platforms. This project aims to implement OSTrails FAIRness assessment tools and integrate the JERICO SKG with the interoperability framework. The expected outcomes include an interoperable schema for SKG, improve data management of glider data and monitor and assess data lifecycle and outcomes.

The SSHOMP/OEAW pilot is developing the SSHOC Open Marketplace as a discovery portal for SSH researchers. This project encourages the evaluation of tools according to FAIR principles and aims to enrich the Marketplace with new entities and improved interactions with the OpenAIRE Graph.

In conclusion, the survey highlights the diverse approaches and strategies employed by different pilot projects to enhance the implementation of FAIR principles and integrate with OSTrails developments. Common themes include the development of SKGs, the enhancement of metadata and data management practices, and the integration of FAIR assessment tools.

4. Dissemination and Engagement Roadmap

This roadmap is a work in progress, and it will be updated constantly as the needs of the partners evolve. A first updated version of this roadmap will be integrated also in D5.1 Strategy and Status Report for Communication, Engagement Exploitation V1 (M8). All project deliverables can be found in our [Zenodo community](#)

4.1. Communication & Dissemination

The Communication and Dissemination section outlines the strategies and activities planned to effectively share OSTrails' objectives, progress, and results with relevant stakeholders. The core tasks include:

1. Developing OSTrails' Digital Identity: Creating a website, social media presence, and branded materials (posters, banners, newsletters) aligned with EOSC-A guidelines.
2. Publishing Stories and Interviews: Featuring narratives from pilot projects to showcase achievements and insights.
3. Promoting Key Results and Publications: Disseminating technical and policy briefs, as well as promoting events, trainings, and workshops.
4. KPIs: Defining key performance indicators to measure the success of communication efforts, such as website traffic, social media engagement, and subscriber growth (see par 5.2).
5. Coordination of Scientific Publishing: Overseeing the dissemination of OSTrails' research findings through Open Access scientific publications.
6. Coordination of event visibility: Overseeing the participation to key events and the organisation dedicated events by members of the consortium; updating a calendar of events and monitoring post events surveys and assessment.

This task utilizes various channels from partners and EOSC-A to maximize the visibility of results at the EU level and oversees the coordination and promotion of open-access scientific publishing of OSTrails' outcomes.

In alignment to what is indicated in the project proposal and in line with the overall objectives of the project, the following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are defined to measure the success of the dissemination and communication activities.

Table 2. Communication and Dissemination KPIs

TYPE	KPI	DESCRIPTION
Branding	6 templates for OSTrails documents, reports, presentations, posters & infographics	Develop a brand identity for OSTrails website, deliverables, presentations, brochure/cards, poster templates, factsheets, technical & policy briefs. OSTrails brand identity will align with EOSC-A guidelines for cobranding in terms of colours, fonts, look & feel
Website	1500 monthly visits	The OSTrails website will serve as a reference point for all project activities providing up to date information on the project, partners, progress, goals, news, adoption stories, events & outputs (e.g., deliverables, briefs), and will include bidirectional links to Zenodo, GitHub repositories and other platforms utilised in OSTrails
Social Media	2000 Twitter followers (>500 total Tweets); >800 YouTube views (>10 posts)	Create Twitter & YouTube channels to communicate OSTrail's progress and regularly populate with new content about ongoing activities
Newsletter	500 subscribers	Issue a monthly newsletter to inform relevant stakeholders about the progress, key results and opportunities for collaboration (e.g., hackathons). The networks of consortium partners will be used to engage subscribers to amplify the outreach. Individual news items will be communicated via partner's (>10K recipients)
Adoption Stories	24 stories, updated 2-3 times	Each pilot will produce their adoption story to explain in simple language the goals and objectives of their pilot, any challenges faced during implementation, and promote the collaborations, procedures and tools that they used to achieve them. These will encourage new stakeholders with similar interests and needs to adopt the specifications and results of OSTrails
Video, Infographics and Podcasts	2 videos, 3 infographics, 4 podcasts	In year 1, develop a video for project visual presentation & promotion, updated with results on year 3. From year 2 develop 3 infographics with data from pilots to showcase uptake/trends and join forces with OpenAIRE, GraspOS and SciLake and INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-02 to produce podcasts (compile interviews from pilots, experts and members of the mentorship programme) on: FAIR metrics & assessment; research products in R&I ecosystem (e.g., software); DMPs as companion tools; curation & quality for SKGs

4.2. Community Engagement roadmap

This section details the roadmap for engaging the research community and other stakeholders such as data stewards, data librarians and developers of resources for the co-creation, adoption and uptake of the OSTrails tools, guidance, best practices.

- Training & Integrated Competence Centre: Establishing a training common to support the delivery of training programs, including online courses, bootcamps, and mentorship programs
- User Engagement Activities: Organizing hackathons, focus groups, and workshops to involve researchers, data stewards, and developers in the co-creation and validation of OSTrails tools and methodologies
- Liaison Activities: Engaging with key stakeholders through policy and technical briefs, annual reports, and participation in national and international events

The success of the community engagement and training initiatives is measured through specific KPIs:

- Training Outputs: Development of a training library, online courses, bootcamps, and tutorials
- Hackathons and Workshops: Organization of hackathons and workshops to gather community input and validate tools
- Mentorship Program: Establishment of a mentorship program targeting infrastructure managers and research support staff
- Community Networks: Formation of a network of trainers linked to national and research community competence centres

Table 3. Community engagement KPIs

TYPE	KPI	DESCRIPTION
Webinars	6 webinars (>300 audience)	Organise 3 webinars per year from Y2 to establish a dialogue with community of developers and support staff. Participate in OpenAIRE's quarterly webinars to Horizon Europe prospective PIs (> 300 people at a time)
Courses and Training Modules	2 courses, 6 modules (> 150 individuals)	Develop courses and modules to educate pilot participants and external stakeholders on the benefits of adopting the OSTrails Interoperability Specs, on how to use the services developed in WP2 and WP3 and introductory modules on maDMPs. The training materials will be hosted on OpenPlato and on the mobile platform EPOC

Guidance Toolkits	1000 downloads	Produce 3 guidance toolkits gathering learning resources to support the adoption of OSTrails interoperability specifications and services
Mentorship program	20-40 participants	Ensure (one-to-one) mentorship with the participation of infrastructure managers, research support staff from institutions and support officers from funders
Train-the-trainer bootcamps	2 bootcamps of 25-35 individuals each, selected from pilots and Ris	Provide training tutorials on the topics of DMPs, SKGs, FAIR Assessment to train specialists and establish networks of trainers that can become key resource of integrated competences centres
Standardisation workshops and hackathons	4 workshops (>2 events per year for Y1 and Y2), >25-30 participants from selected communities per event	Organise 4 standardisation workshops for community input towards linking best practices, guidelines, and recommendations on maFAIRTest, FAIR assessment vocabulary, SKGs
Hackathons	4 hackathons (>40-50 participants)	Organise 2 “Apples to Apples” hackathons with the EOSC-A FAIR Metrics & Data Quality TF to co-create/validate tests. Co-organise with SciLake a hackathon to validate SKG data model and APIs. Co-organise with RDA a maDMP hackathon to validate maDMP executables
Co-organise workshops	>15 national workshops (>500 attendees); >8 Cluster related workshops x 2 (>300 attendees); 3 workshops in 2 EOSC Symposium events (> 400 attendees); 2 workshops in OSFAIR2025 (> 300 attendees)	Organise co-located workshops in the context of national and ESFRI events: 15 national pilots and 8 ESFRI Clusters in respective annual events. Organise workshops in EOSC Symposium, OSFAIR
Presentation in external conferences/workshops	15 conference/workshop participations (> 1000 attendees)	Ensure OSTrails consortium members participation and presentation of results in external events such as: RDA conferences, ESFRI Clusters annual events, Open Science Conference, FDO Forum, Open Repositories, OSFAIR conference
Policy & Technical briefs	3 policy & 4 technical briefs (>1000 downloads)	Create 3 policy briefs for funders and RPOs executives, highlighting issues of FAIR assessment, SKG for quality and interoperability, DMP as an evaluation mechanism. Create 4 technical briefs

		for infrastructure providers, highlighting each of OSTrails pillars
Policy Reports	2 reports (>600 downloads)	Publish an initial report on the Plan-Track-Assess pathways: gaps in DOs coverage, community FAIRness enablers/blockers, and a final report at M34 with guidelines and lessons learnt to be left as legacy to future initiatives and to relevant stakeholders
Scientific publications	>6 publications by M36	Ensure publication of innovation papers in leading peer reviewed journals related to Open Science, data management, Reproducibility, Knowledge Graphs and Semantic Web Technologies, Scholarly Infrastructures

4.3. Exploitation roadmap

The exploitation roadmap focuses on ensuring the long-term impact and sustainability of OSTrails’ results. These aspects are clearly linked to the integration of OSTrails key results in the broader scope of EOSC, their adoption by key institutional stakeholders and by EOSC nodes both at the national and European level. The collaboration with other EOSC projects will also be crucial in this respect. To ensure this result, the following actions will be undertaken:

- Integration of OSTrails Outputs: Pilot owners and partners will integrate OSTrails’ tools, methods, and protocols within their organizations and promote them through national and international networks.
- Collaboration with EOSC and EOSC projects: OSTrails will ensure regular exchanges with relevant EOSC projects on relevant topics to promote adoption of developed solutions and to avoid duplication of efforts; in particular exchanges with the OSCARS project will facilitate the adoption also by disciplinary infrastructures not represented in OSTrails; Skills4EOSC competence centres will facilitate reuse of developed training materials as well as their long term preservation; collaboration with EVERSE will ensure quality and long-term support for software; alignment with FAIRCORE4EOSC will a data type registry for SKGs; last but not least, FAIR IMPACT can help maximise the adoption of OSTrails tools to scientific communities. The liaison office (T5.4) activities will ensure alignment with these and other EOSC project and initiatives and promote the organisation of joint events and activities. Collaborations with other Key Stakeholders: WP5 will engage (also within the framework of dedicated events) with networks such as COARA,

Science Europe, and EARMA to facilitate practical uptake within universities and research institutions.

- Commercial Opportunities: SMEs in the consortium will seek to exploit results to enhance their business models, particularly in providing open-source services for the research community.
- Open-Source Licensing: OSTrails will ensure that all resources and software produced by the project are made available under open-source licenses, promoting maximum compatibility and reusability. Dedicated events such as hackathons will facilitate the adoption of the technological solutions developed within the project.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the OSTrails project has made significant progress in its first six months, setting the foundation for future developments.

The project's architecture and interoperability frameworks are in the initial drafting phase, with key APIs being developed to enhance data management and scientific knowledge sharing. The ongoing "Digital Object Survey" will inform the creation of a contextually-sensitive FAIRness model, moving beyond compliance to provide actionable guidance. Pilot activities have seen strong engagement, with national and thematic pilots aligning their objectives and integration plans. Lastly, the project has established a comprehensive dissemination and engagement roadmap to ensure broad adoption and utilization of its outcomes.

This document reflects the current state of developments, with the understanding that the presented results are interim and will continue to evolve.

6. References

Schultes, E., Magagna, B., Hettne, K.M., Pergl, R., Suchánek, M., Kuhn, T., 2020. Reusable FAIR Implementation Profiles as Accelerators of FAIR Convergence, in: Grossmann, G., Ram, S. (Eds.), *Advances in Conceptual Modeling*. Springer International Publishing, Cham, pp. 138–147. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-65847-2_13